

Influence of Single Wall Carbon Nanotubes and Thermal Treatment on the Morphology of Polymer Thin Films

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Abstract

Homogeneous and stable thin films of poly(butylene terephthalate) PBT and its nanocomposites based on single wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) were prepared by spin coating. PBT thin films show crystalline structures for thicknesses above 40 nm, consisting of submicrometer size 2D-spherulites. In the case of nanocomposites, carbon nanotubes act as nucleating agents and provide a template for the crystallization of PBT. This gives rise to hybrid shish-kebab structures, even in the thinnest films (~10 nm thick). Melting and recrystallization provoke the crystallization of PBT and its nanocomposites, and can be used to control morphology. For PBT thin films, the orientation of crystalline lamellae undergoes a transformation, changing from a disposition perpendicular to the substrate ("edge-on") to a parallel arrangement ("flat-on") after recrystallization. In the case of the nanocomposites, the CNT influence on the polymer crystallization morphology in thin films is less significant than in the bulk due to the effect of the substrate interactions. Using Raman microscopy it is possible to directly observe both, the degree of dispersion and the location of carbon nanotubes in

the films. The results reveal that bigger agglomerates act as more effective nucleating points than isolated bundles of SWCNTs during crystallization of the polymer matrix.

Keywords: A. Carbon nanotubes; A. Coating; A. Polymer-matrix composites (PMCs); D. Atomic force microscopy (AFM); D. Raman spectroscopy.

1. Introduction

Polymer thin films have attracted great attention owing to the important role in a variety of technological applications, such as adhesion, electronics, liquid crystal alignment, and coatings [1, 2]. When a polymer crystallizes in thin films, the orientation of lamellae is crucial to the film properties. It has been generally observed that thin films of several hundreds of nanometers exhibit predominantly edge-on lamellae while ultrathin films exhibit flat-on lamellae. Nevertheless, there are several factors, besides thickness [3], such as the interaction with the substrate [4] or the crystallization temperature [5] that may control the crystalline lamellae orientation.

A polymer/CNT nanocomposite often exhibits properties that differ substantially from those of the pristine polymer matrix [6]. One of the most important parameters dictating those properties is the level of CNT dispersion in the polymer matrix. CNTs and single wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) in particular, are usually synthesized in bundles [6]. Dispersive van der Waals forces hold the bundles together. Because of their long length and high polarizability, the amount of energy required to separate an individual tube from the bundle is relatively high. Furthermore, because of its long length, a single nanotube can have one section that resides in a bundle whilst another section remains isolated.

In addition to dispersion on the nanoscale, i.e., bundled versus isolated nanotubes, dispersion is also important over larger length scales. For example, CNTs segregated at the interface of sintered polymer particles or segregated to one phase of a two-phase co-continuous blend, can significantly change the relationship between electrical conductivity and tube weight fraction. Hence it is useful to consider two length scales of dispersion, the nanoscale (10^{-9} m) and microscale (10^{-6} m). It is also worth pointing out that the final dispersion of CNTs in a polymer is not only a function of the method(s) used to separate individual tubes, but also depends upon the method(s) used to mix the tubes with the polymer and the way in which the nanocomposite is processed into its final shape.

The level of CNT dispersion in a nanocomposite is interrelated to the level of CNT aggregation. This in turn has a direct effect on different properties of the materials. This includes their mechanical properties [7] and conductivity in both, bulk form [8] and in thin films [9]. Several previous studies have shown that CNTs act as nucleating agents and enhance the degree of polymer matrix crystallinity [10, 11]. The effect of CNTs in templating polymer crystallization has also been investigated [12, 13]. In addition to the level of CNT aggregation, changes induced by the presence of CNTs, i.e. changes in the degree of crystallinity and morphology, will also affect the physical properties of the nanocomposite [14].

This work reports on the morphology of a series of thin and ultrathin films of spin-coated poly(butylene terephthalate) PBT and its nanocomposites based on SWCNTs. The aim of this work is to study the dispersion of CNTs in polymer nanocomposite thin films at the micro-scale. It will also attempt to correlate dispersion with morphological changes induced in thin films by CNT/substrate interactions, at both micro- and nano-length scales.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Materials and Sample Preparation

Nanocomposites of poly(butylene terephthalate) (PBT) ($M_w \approx 15000$ g/mol, $T_m \approx 225$ °C) and oxidized single-wall carbon nanotubes (CNI Technology Co., Texas, USA, synthesized using the HiPco method) were prepared by in-situ polymerization as described previously [15]. The diameter of the SWCNTs, as characterized by Raman Spectroscopy, ranges from about 0.6 nm to 1.4 nm [16]. A SWCNT weight concentration of 0.2 % was chosen because it is the highest achievable by this method.

Thin films were prepared by spin coating the polymer matrix and nanocomposite in trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) on silicon wafers (100). First, a polymer solution (20 g/l), referred to hereafter as (1:0), was prepared. From this, a number of less concentrated solutions were obtained by selective dilution. These were: 10 g/l (1:1), 6.7 g/l (1:2), 2.2 g/l (1:8) and 1.1 g/l (1:16). A syringe was then used to dispense 0.1 ml of each solution onto the center of the silicon substrate (20×25 mm² in size) whilst it was rotating at a speed of 2400 rpm. The silicon wafers were obtained from Wafer World, Inc. They had both surfaces polished and were used as supplied. The thickness of the native silicon oxide surface was determined by ellipsometry to be ≈ 2 nm [17] after cleaning with soap solution (commercial detergent: Procter & Gamble) and bidistilled water.

The thickness of each of the polymer-only films was determined by ellipsometry. These were found to increase with polymer concentration within the 10-150 nm range (see Figure 1). Similar thicknesses were obtained for the nanocomposite thin films prepared from equivalent concentrations.

In order to promote crystallization of the thin films, they were thermally treated by using a Mettler FP5 chamber (Mettler Instruments AG).

2.2. Techniques

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) was carried out using a NanoScope IIIA Multimode from Veeco operating in the tapping mode. This was used to investigate the surface morphology of the spin coated films at room temperature. AFM images were analyzed by means of the software NanoScope Analysis v1.10.

Raman spectroscopy was carried out using a Renishaw InVia Raman Microscope at the ID13 beamline of the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF). The instrument was configured with a 500 mW near-IR 785 nm diode laser, holographic Rayleigh rejection filters, a motorized sample stage and a 1200 lines/mm grating. The laser spot size was $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter.

Measurements of sample thickness were done by using a spectroscopic ellipsometer [18] at angles of 60° and 70° and at wavelengths between 400 and 800 nm, in order to avoid the transparency region of Si.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Morphology of PBT and PBT/SWCNT thin films

Figure 2 shows AFM height images of the thin films prepared from the (1:0), (1:1), (1:2), and (1:16) solutions. These correspond to both pure PBT samples and nanocomposite samples having a 0.2 % weight of SWCNT (left and right columns respectively). The images reveal that, in all but the thinnest films, the coatings cover the substrate homogeneously. For the thinnest films of both materials, meanwhile, a small fraction of randomly distributed holes are observed. Some authors have previously pointed out that these pores could be a consequence of the presence of air bubbles or

impurities [19]. This is significant as for most coating applications homogeneity, uniformity, and durability of the thin films are essential features.

In general, the stability of a liquid film over a substrate depends upon its thickness. When the thickness is high enough, gravitational forces stabilize the film against dewetting effects [20]. When thickness becomes comparable to the characteristic length, λ_c , of the capillary waves of the fluid material ($\lambda_c = (\gamma/\rho g)^{1/2}$, where γ is the surface tension, ρ the density and g the gravity acceleration), molecular interactions between the material and the substrate dominate. Under these conditions long range forces, such as van der Waals interactions, can break up the film by dewetting effects. Despite this, it is still possible to obtain homogeneous films when using spin coating techniques under appropriate conditions [21].

Although PBT is a semicrystalline polymer, crystallization is inhibited for the thinnest films of pure PBT (about 10 nm thickness). This is due to confinement effects, as reported previously for semicrystalline polymers [22]. The first crystalline motives for pure PBT thin films appear in samples of 40 nm thickness (1:2 dilution), as evidenced in Fig. 2 as bright spots. This can be seen in more detail in Figure 3a, where spherulitic superstructures having a radial distribution of crystalline lamellae can be distinguished. The diameter of these motives varies from 100 to 2000 nm.

In the case of PBT/SWCNT nanocomposites, the presence of SWCNTs induces PBT crystallization even in the thinnest films. This provides evidence for SWCNTs acting as a nucleating agent [23]. It also provides a template for oriented polymer crystallization, not only in the bulk material [13] but also for ultrathin polymer films [24]. Figure 3b shows an AFM height image of a 10 nm thick film of PBT nanocomposite with 0.2% weight of SWCNTs. The presence of a characteristic CNT bundle lying on the surface is clear. An inset image within the figure shows a region of

this structure in more detail. In this it is possible to observe so called hybrid shish-kebab structures, resulting from oriented crystallization of PBT on nanotube walls. This morphology is similar to that found in other systems based on polyethylene/CNT [25, 26]. In this case, polymer chains are oriented parallel to the CNT surfaces and the resulting crystalline lamellae grow perpendicular to the nanotubes' main axis.

The influence of CNTs in templating oriented polymer crystallization and their role as nucleating agents can also be observed in thicker samples. Figure 2 shows different crystalline morphologies for pure PBT and PBT/0.2% weight SWCNT samples of 40 nm thickness, (a 1:2 dilution). While the pure PBT sample shows 2D-spherulites, shish-kebab structures are seen in the case of the nanocomposite. For samples having a thickness of about 60 nm, (a 1:1 dilution), there are a higher number of crystalline motives present in the nanocomposite AFM image compared to that of the PBT image (figure 2). Meanwhile, for the thickest films (a 1:0 dilution) larger spherulites are observed for pure PBT samples compared to the nanocomposite. This provides further evidence supporting the role of CNTs as a nucleating agent during polymer crystallization.

3.2. Morphology of PBT and PBT/SWCNT recrystallized thin films

Thin films of pure PBT and PBT/SWCNT nanocomposites were thermally treated in order to induce crystallization under controlled conditions. For the recrystallization procedure, samples were held at a temperature of 240 °C for 3 minutes. This is well above the T_m of the polymer matrix. The films were then brought back down to room temperature at a rate of 3 °C/min. Figure 4 shows AFM height images of the recrystallized thin films prepared from the (1:0), (1:1), (1:2), and (1:16) solutions. Images are shown for both pure PBT samples and those of the nanocomposite with

0.2% weight of SWCNT (the left and right columns, respectively). The AFM images reveal that crystallization takes place in all samples, irrespective of film thickness. It is also worth noting that the thinner samples show the presence of holes, which can be interpreted as dewetting. This indicates that both dewetting and crystallization happen simultaneously during thermal treatment.

Both pure PBT and PBT/SWCNT nanocomposites give rise to a spherulitic morphology as they crystallize, as can be clearly seen in figure 4. The recrystallization procedure has an interesting impact on the morphology of the PBT matrix, as it allows the orientation of crystalline lamellae to be controlled. Figure 5a shows AFM phase images of a pure PBT thin film (40 nm thick) before (left) and after (right) thermal treatment. Below each image the phase profile along the white line is presented. The phase contrast between amorphous and crystalline regions in the spin coated PBT film indicates that, in this case, crystalline lamellae are oriented perpendicular to the film surface, in the so called “edge-on” configuration. The distance between hard domains is around 18 nm, in good agreement with the long spacing calculated using the AFM software. Software analysis also permits more detailed information to be obtained about structural parameters. The Power Spectral Density (PSD) is a mathematical function that quantifies repetition frequency as a function of distance. Figure 5b shows the frequency of phase value repetition as a function of the distances (Λ) extracted from figure 5a (left). The maximum in the curve, located at around 20 nm, can be associated with the polymeric long spacing (L).

After recrystallization changes in morphology are evident, as shown in figure 5a (right). Now the lamellae appear oriented parallel to the substrate plane in the so called “flat-on” configuration. In this case no appreciable phase contrast is found and only the edges of the lamellae are visible in the phase profile.

In the case of recrystallization of the nanocomposite samples, the CNTs get wrapped and are not clearly visible in the images. Nevertheless their effect as nucleating and templating agents can be inferred. Figure 4 shows how the size of the spherulites increases with increasing film thickness for both systems. When AFM images of samples (PBT and nanocomposites) of similar thicknesses are compared, those of nanocomposite thin films show a higher number of spherulites with a smaller diameter. This can be attributed to the greater number of nucleating points present in the polymer nanocomposite, because of the presence of carbon nanotubes.

Figure 6 shows an AFM height image of a PBT/0.2 % weight of SWCNT film of 60 nm thickness that has been thermally treated. Below the image, the height profile corresponding to the lines drawn on the image is shown. This shows that the general tendency of crystalline lamellae is to lie parallel to the substrate, as in the pure matrix. There are some regions, however, where the high roughness (red line compared to the black line in Fig. 6) indicates that crystallites grow in a different manner. This is the result of CNT influence during PBT crystallization. In these regions, crystalline lamellae grow perpendicular to the CNT walls, and consequently perpendicular to the substrate. We have previously reported for the same nanocomposite in bulk that even a modest amount of carbon nanotubes (PBT/0.1 SWCNT) produces a strong templating effect on crystallization morphology [13]. However, from the results presented in this work, we may conclude that the CNT influence on the polymer crystallization morphology in thin films is less significant due to the substrate interactions.

3.3. Dispersion and location of SWCNTs in the nanocomposite thin films

Raman Spectroscopy was used as a complementary technique in order to elucidate the location, dispersion degree and effect of CNTs on the crystallization of nanocomposite

thin films. This technique has been shown to be one of the most useful for the study of CNTs [27, 28].

Figure 7a shows an optical micrograph captured by the Raman microscope of a nanocomposite thin film (40 nm thick) after the recrystallization process. It is possible to appreciate the spherulitic morphology of the sample, as well as the presence of some motives (indicated by circles in the image). These are mainly located at the center of the spherulites. Raman spectra were collected from a region of the area shown in Figure 7a measuring $29 \times 24 \mu\text{m}^2$ using a scanning acquisition mode and with a step size of $1 \mu\text{m}$. The range of this scanned region is shown in the figure as a box. Figure 8 shows the Raman spectra obtained from different regions of the sample, marked as *1* and *2* in Figure 7a. Region *1* is located at the nucleus of the central spherulite, while region *2* is located far from it and close to the boundary between spherulites. The characteristic bands corresponding to SWCNT, namely the RBMs, the D and the G and G' bands are listed in the spectrum corresponding to region *1*.

Figure 7b shows the resulting intensity map obtained after plotting the intensity of the G' band versus the base line. This shows that there is an appreciable G' band intensity over approximately 75 % of the scan area, thus indicating that dispersion of the nanotubes within these areas is good. The higher signal obtained around the nucleus of the spherulites indicates a higher concentration of nanotubes in these areas. In addition, the deformation of CNTs due to stresses and constrains in composites can be monitored by the shift in the position of the G' band [29, 30]. We have analyzed the behavior of the G' band in two different regions of the sample, obtaining values of 2574 cm^{-1} and 2577 cm^{-1} for the position of the G' band in regions *1* and *2* of Figure 7a respectively. Results that would indicate some compression of the CNTs at the boundary between

spherulites (region 2) due to higher amount of constrains than at the nucleus of the spherulite (region 1).

The so called Radial Breathing Modes (RBM), located at frequencies below 400 cm^{-1} , are related to coherent vibrations of the carbon atoms across the radial direction of the nanotubes. These bands are useful for obtaining information about the diameter and electronic structure of the SWCNTs, as well as their aggregation level [31, 32]. The area of the Raman spectrum corresponding to the RBM region is shown in detail below each spectrum in Figure 8. Characteristic Raman bands from single wall carbon nanotubes are clearly seen in both cases. There is some variation of the intensity ratios for the different peaks depending upon the position at which the spectrum was obtained. The higher intensity of the G' band in region 1 compared to region 2 indicates a higher concentration of SWCNTs in this area. The so-called "roping peak", located around 266 cm^{-1} has been used as an indicator of the packing level and size of the ropes of SWCNTs [33]. Previous works have shown that when the size of the agglomerates decreases, there is a decrease in the intensity of this peak and, simultaneously, an increase in the intensity of the peak located around 234 cm^{-1} [34]. Furthermore, a decrease in the ratio of intensities between the two peaks (I_{266}/I_{234}) indicates a decrease in the size of CNT agglomerates. This effect can be observed by comparing the intensities of both bands, represented in the enlargement of the RBM region of Figure 8. In addition, Figure 7c shows the intensity ratio I_{266}/I_{234} along the white line drawn at position 1 in the optical micrograph of Figure 7a. It is seen that the I_{266}/I_{234} maximum coincides with the nucleus of the spherulite. This fact, together with the carbon nanotube distribution shown in the intensity map (Figure 7b), supports the idea that bigger agglomerates act as more effective nucleating points than isolated bundles of nanotubes during crystallization of the polymer matrix.

4. Conclusions

Stable and homogeneous thin films (about 10 to 200 nm in thickness) of PBT and a nanocomposite with 0.2 % weight of SWCNT were prepared by spin coating. The presence of small pores in the thinnest samples (~10 nm thick) can be explained as a consequence of the presence of air bubbles or impurities. PBT thin films show crystalline structures for thicknesses above 40 nm, consisting of submicrometer sized 2D-spherulites. In the case of nanocomposites, CNTs act as nucleating agents and provide a template for PBT crystallization, giving rise to hybrid shish-kebab structures even in the thinnest films. A melting and recrystallization procedure provokes crystallization of PBT and its nanocomposites, and can be used to control morphology. The orientation of PBT crystalline lamellae undergoes a transformation due to thermal treatment, changing from a disposition perpendicular to the substrate ("edge-on") to a parallel arrangement ("flat-on") after recrystallization. In the case of the nanocomposites, the CNT influence on the polymer crystallization morphology in thin films is less significant than in the bulk due to the substrate interactions. By using Raman microscopy it is possible to visualize directly both, the degree of dispersion and the location of carbon nanotubes in the thin films. The results suggest that bigger agglomerates act as more effective nucleating points than isolated bundles of SWCNTs during crystallization of the polymer matrix.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank the financial support from the MICINN (grant MAT2009-07789, MAT2008-03232) and from the CSIC (PIE200950I088), Spain. J.J.H acknowledges MICINN for FPI fellowship. Measurements of sample thickness were performed by Dr.

R. Serna. Fruitful discussions with Prof. C. Domingo concerning Raman data are also acknowledged. We thank Prof. R. Roslaniec (West Pomeranian University, Poland) for preparing and providing the samples.

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Caption to figures

Figure 1. Thicknesses of PBT thin films as a function of polymer concentration measured by ellipsometry. The values are equivalent for the nanocomposite thin films.

Figure 2. AFM height images of (left) PBT and (right) PBT/0.2 % weight of SWCNT spin coated films prepared from different dilutions. Scanned area is $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$.

Figure 3. (a) AFM height image of a PBT thin film 40 nm thick showing spherulite structures. (b) AFM height image showing a characteristic SWCNT bundle in a PBT/0.2

SWCNT % w/w thin film 10 nm thick. The inset shows a magnification of the hybrid shish-kebab structure

Figure 4. AFM height images of (left) PBT and (right) PBT/0.2 % weight of SWCNT in films prepared from different dilutions after thermal treatment. Scanned area is $25 \times 25 \mu\text{m}^2$.

Figure 5. (a) AFM phase images of a PBT thin film 40 nm thick before (left) and after (right) thermal treatment. Schematic view of the so called “flat on” and “edge on” configurations is presented. At the bottom of each image is shown the phase lag profile obtained along the drawn lines. (b) AFM frequency of repetition of the phase lag value as a function of the distances obtained from (a) left image.

Figure 6. AFM height image of a PBT/0.2 % weight of SWCNT thin film (60 nm thick) after thermal treatment. At the bottom of the image the height profile along the red and black lines is presented.

Figure 7. (a) Optical micrograph of the PBT/0.2 SWCNT thin film (40 nm thick) after the recrystallization process, indicating the scanned area, the nucleation points and the areas where Raman spectra are studied in more detail (white line, 1 and 2). (b) Intensity map obtained after plotting the intensity of the G' band versus the base line for the Raman spectra collected while scanning a $29 \times 24 \mu\text{m}^2$ area with a $1 \mu\text{m}$ step size. (c) Intensity ratio between the peaks located at 266 and 234 cm^{-1} obtained along the line indicated in the optical micrograph at position *1*.

Figure 8. Raman spectra obtained from different zones indicated as *1* and *2* in the optical micrograph of figure 7a. At the bottom of each spectrum is shown a magnification of the RBM spectral region.